
METHODOLOGY FOR THE USE OF BUSINESS COMMUNICATIONS AND THE APPLICATION OF KPI IN THE ACTIVITIES OF ENTERPRISES.

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Abstract

This article provides information on business communications, their content and essence, the benefits of communications, the use of organizational communications, and the methodology of applying KPIs in the activities of enterprises.

Keywords

Business communication, Business communication, Importance of communication, Importance of business communication, Internal Communications, KPI - Key Performance Indicators,

Business communication is the interaction of subjects of communication to achieve certain interests of the company, its main goals.

It is worth distinguishing between the concept of business communication and business communication, since communication is within the scope of the study of psychological science, while communication implies a certain aspect and can be considered from technical, informational, economic, organizational and many other points of view. In addition, it is important to note the focus of communication on a specific result. Communication becomes communication only if some action has been taken. In the case of business communication, it can be considered as such if results have been achieved that are useful for achieving the goals of the enterprise. The meaning of business communication is to convey a message that contributes to its perception by the recipient and contributes to the desired, purposeful actions. Therefore, when transmitting a message in business communications, it is important to give the partner the conditions for perception, understanding and implementation.⁷⁹

⁷⁹ <https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki/Бизнес-коммуникация>

In any organization, communication is, first of all, the interaction of employees, which cannot be ignored, which is expressed in any form and without which joint activities are impossible. And business communications involve the exchange of information, experience, discussion of results and problem solving.

Business communications are divided into business conversations, public speaking, negotiations and various kinds of meetings. To optimize the incoming information flows, the scientific community has developed communication networks that regulate the sequence of receipt and receipt of messages.⁸⁰

The importance of business communications includes:

- Efficient and uninterrupted operation of the enterprise
- Basis for decision making
- Proper planning
- Increased productivity at minimal cost
- Morale boost
- Democratic governance
- Bringing people together
- Building mutual trust and confidence
- Facilitation of management activities
- Assistance in smooth operation
- Improving management efficiency
- Maintenance of production peace
- Assistance to management
- Help with job satisfaction
- Save time

The importance of communication includes:

1. Efficient and Smooth Running of an Enterprise
2. Basis of Decision Making
3. Proper Planning and Coordination
4. For Higher Productivity at Minimum Cost
5. Morale Building
6. Democratic Management
7. Binds People Together
8. Creates Mutual Trust and Confidence⁸¹

⁸⁰ <https://www.evkova.org/kursovye-raboty/osobennosti-kommunikatsij-v-organizatsii-rol-i-znachenie-delovyyih-kommunikatsij-v-razviti-i-organizatsii>

⁸¹ <https://www.economicdiscussion.net/>

The effectiveness of business communications is aimed at the implementation of constitutional human rights and freedoms in the field of culture and art, the most important of which are the right to access cultural values, freedom of literary and artistic forms of creativity, teaching, and protection of intellectual property. Aesthetic associations working in contact with museums, the church, art exhibitions, festivals and talent competitions - the entire system of aesthetic education determines the high development of creative experience, influencing the creation of an environment for self-realization of the individual in communications.⁸²

One of the indicators of the socialization of the individual is social and political activity. Socio-political activity is an indicator of activity for the benefit of an individual, team, association, society, carried out voluntarily in accordance with spiritual motives. Its qualitative content changes along with the growth of the individual's consciousness. The degree of socio-political activity may vary, for example, from participation in meetings, meetings to the implementation of one-time public assignments and, finally, to the implementation of permanent assignments.

Thus, according to a very large number of indicators in the entire system of criteria, it is possible to evaluate the effectiveness of communications. Since the measurements of the effectiveness of business communications are diverse in the system of criteria, we introduce the most generalized indicators for this system, reflecting its functions.

Benefits of Internal Communications for Employers and Employees.⁸³

⁸² https://bstudy.net/850905/sotsiologiya/effektivnost_delovyh_kommunikatsiy#528430

⁸³ <https://www.lumapps.com/internal-communication/metrics-kpis-for-internal-communications/>

Successful internal communications increases employee teamwork and productivity

Internal communication improves employees' overall experience at work

The way top executives and managers communicate with team members has a significant impact on employee engagement

KPI - Key Performance Indicators - Key Performance Indicators - An evaluation criterion used to determine the performance of a university employee based on quantitative and qualitative indicators.

KPI (plus) - a set of criteria that increase the efficiency of labor activity;

KPI (minus) - a set of criteria that reduce the efficiency of labor activity;

Incentives are a system of socio-economic forms and measures aimed at ensuring the interest of employees in the results of their work, active involvement in work, improving the quality of work and services.

The evaluation commission is a group of heads of departments in the organizational structure of the university to evaluate the effectiveness of the KPI of the faculty and staff.

Employees are divided into the following two groups:

a) Employees of group 1 - employees specified, without an assessment of the main performance indicators (KPI);

(b) Employees in Group 2 are those whose key performance indicators (KPIs).

According to the decision of the competent governing body of the enterprises (Councils), the effectiveness of the executive staff is recognized as follows:

1. At a low level of 40 percent to 60 percent.
2. From 61% to 80% - at an unsatisfactory level.
3. From 81% to 90% - satisfactorily.
4. From 91 percent to 100 percent - enough.
5. If more than 100 percent - at a high level.

This was approved by the enterprises Supervisory Board in order to encourage conscientious performance of official duties, increase the efficiency and quality of work, strengthen the environment for professional growth and healthy competition.

KPI is used to determine the employees staff of the enterprises, monthly bonuses (six months) and bonuses at the expense of the financial incentive fund formed on the basis of financial resources of the enterprises.

KPI is not used in the calculation of the following payments, which are regulated by law. These are:

- monthly specified in the staffing table;
- social benefits;
- Privileges for additional working hours, nights, holidays;
- social payments and benefits;
- payment of vacation or sick leave.

The purpose of financial incentives for enterprises staff:

- Ensuring that each employee is truly rewarded for the results of their effective work during their work;

- Improving the remuneration of enterprises staff;

As a result of the study, the goal has been achieved: a system of key performance indicators has been developed as a tool to improve the management efficiency of production, administrative and managerial personnel employees.

In the process of studying the theoretical and methodological foundations of the economic approach to personnel management, it was revealed that the strategic approach to management is understood as a set of techniques and methods of influencing personnel through a specific comparison of processes and results. At the same time, the strategic approach assumes that the labor resources of the organization should be used effectively. That is, personnel management from a strategic point of view can be recognized as effective if not only the teaching process is successfully converted into results, but the results obtained correspond to the strategic goals of the management system and the organization as a whole.

In the scientific literature, there is still no unambiguous and generally accepted terminology regarding key performance indicators. In the author's interpretation, KPIs are considered as a tool for improving the efficiency of personnel activities, focused on the formation of a team consisting of involved and executive employees.

In personnel management, an important role is given to key performance indicators that contribute to improving the efficiency of personnel management, as they are an effective way to achieve the goals and objectives of the institution. KPI

allows you to manage efficiency: identify weaknesses in business management and organization, set measurable goals, and then evaluate and motivate them to achieve them through personal interest in the results of work. World practice proves that the implementation of KPI helps to achieve the goals of organizations 10-30% faster and more efficiently. In addition, the implementation of the KPI system helps to reduce costs by 10-15%, increase labor productivity, reduce the time for implementing business processes, improve the quality of teaching, etc. That is, a genuine KPI has an "avalanche" effect.

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